

The Island Approach (TIA): a suited projective technique for evaluating a bevy of attributes

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Abstract

In this paper, we present The Island Approach (TIA), a projective technique that finds its origin in *Survivor Island* (Kalter, 2016) and is especially suitable for evaluating a large number of attributes or features of an innovation or service. We illustrate the procedures of the island approach based on the evaluation of user requirements and scenarios in HRADIO, a Horizon 2020 funded project that aims to leverage the full potential of hybrid radio. In this project, we apply a living lab-approach to determine which ideas are relevant to develop as features or services in real life. We successfully conducted the island approach in co-creation workshops to perform a qualitative evaluation of 29 hybrid radio scenarios. We evaluate TIA itself as well, summarize its strengths and weaknesses, reflect on our experiences while conducting its procedures and provide practical tips and guidelines to implement TIA. We conclude that the island approach is a useful and suited evaluation tool for the learning curve and maturity of innovations (Jespersen, 2008). In addition, we illustrate how TIA could contribute to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDG Knowledge Hub, 2018).

Keywords: *living lab - maturity of innovation - user research - co-creation - projective techniques - evaluation methods and tools*

1 Introduction

In this paper we present 'The Island Approach' (TIA), an approach we developed and applied to generate and prioritize user requirements and user scenarios.

Our motivation to apply an approach like TIA was mostly practice-orientated and originates from the fact that in our research projects that deal with innovative technologies and services, we are often confronted with a long list of ideas and features at the start of a project. To streamline this multitude of ideas and to ensure that all relevant stakeholders, including end-users, have a voice in this, we are constantly looking for innovative methods and techniques. TIA is one of those techniques we started applying in our living lab research projects (Pierson & Lievens, 2009). We see TIA as a useful approach in the exploration phase of the living lab, to evolve from idea towards concept or prototype (Schuurman, 2017:8). More in particular, we see it as a tool to reduce a multitude of ideas in a first stage of the process and to proceed with those ideas that are relevant from a user perspective. TIA helps us in applying a user-centered design approach and allows for user involvement from the start of a project, keeping in mind the specific context in which the innovation will be used (Norman, 2002).

In the first section, we discuss the origin of TIA. To continue, we focus on the alterations and extensions we applied to adapt the original island approach as developed by Kalter (2016) to our own needs. In the third section, we illustrate the specific application of TIA in a project. Finally, we provide an evaluation of its strength and weaknesses.

2 The Origin of TIA: Survivor Island (Steve Kalter, 2016)

The Island Approach is inspired by Survivor Island, a projective technique developed by Steve Kalter (2016). He provides an in-depth explanation of the procedures of Survivor Island in the chapter 'Using Projectives to Uncover "Aha Moments" in Qualitative Research' (Kalter, 2016). The goal of survivor island is to reduce ideas or features, by way of voting them of the island. According to Kalter (2016:131) projective techniques like survivor island are fun, easy-going "assignments" to approach, explore and uncover deeper feelings and perceptions of i.e., focus-group participants in qualitative research. "Their goal is to elicit deeper, more visceral feelings from respondents [...] viewpoints that may go unmentioned when using more direct lines of inquiry." (Kalter, 2016: 131). Projectives "stimulate" respondents to "project" themselves into a situation and the results of these exercises serve as a "springboard for deeper discussion" (Kalter, 2016:132).

Projective techniques, also referred to as ‘associative’ techniques, are indeed an appropriate manner to ‘elicit’ spontaneous and improvident reactions (Baarda et al, 2013; Stalpers, 2007). Projective techniques are often applied in market research to uncover latent feelings and emotions (Boddy, 2005; Donoghue; 2000). These techniques provide insight in the primary experiences of individuals. At the same time, they “enable participants to say more about the research subject than they can say spontaneously, accessing thoughts, feelings or meanings which are not immediately available” (AQR glossary, s.d). In addition, they are useful to make an interview session livelier and to keep the respondents more motivated. Kalter believes that “This active involvement, set in a fun, creative context tends to encourage respondents to become more open and revealing about their natural instincts, innate perceptions, and personal desires”. Thus, he rightfully emphasizes that “When successful, projectives are often the most enlightening portion of a focus group, and seem much more likely to deliver that highly desirable but ever elusive “aha moment” than more direct lines of inquiry typically accomplish.” (Kalter, 2016:131).

Projective techniques can be used for different purposes in research, depending on its specific characteristics. The Survivor Island technique is considered especially suitable when the aim of research is to evaluate and reduce a large collection of potential attributes, components, or features e.g., during the evaluation phase of a new product or service. This is because Survivor Island essentially is a purging process, ideas get voted off or on the island (Kalter, 2016).

Kalter (2016) asserts that some very insightful perceptions, both favorable and unfavorable, are likely to emerge from the Survivor Island exercise. He describes the procedures for Survivor Island as follows (pp. 140-141):

First, a giant “island” shape is sketched on a whiteboard or large easel sheet;
The moderator then places each of the features being tested on separate post-its and places them within the borders of the island;

To narrow down the large field, the participants must decide which post-its should be “voted off” the island, keeping only the bare essentials in mind. To start with, all the individual features are removed where there is 100% consensus by the group for their removal. Additionally, the features are eliminated when a majority of participants recommend their removal;

The role of the moderator during this “purging process” is to manage the process by encouraging the participants to continue the exercise until it is felt that only the strongest and most crucial features remain. The moderator must also ensure that participants explain their motivations for voting certain features on the island, and for excluding others from it.

The technique is loosely based on the CBS Survivor television series⁵². A remarkable advantage of Survivor Island is that when doing this exercise, the moderator can continually encourage respondents to voice their rationale for keeping desirable attributes on the island, and casting off the remainder attributes. The process of whittling down the features is continued until a desired number of attributes is reached. Or until it is felt, i.e. during a co-creation workshop (Sanders & Stappers, 2008, 2014), that a consensus among the participants exists about which features are the strongest or the most crucial to remain. In other words, only those who are most worthy to survive the island, remain on the island. Hence, the naming of the technique 'Survivor Island', in namesake of the similar composition of the aforementioned television series.

To conclude, Kalter (2016) emphasizes that the Survivor Island technique has proven itself very useful for winnowing out a large number of possibilities and ideas. We are inclined to agree with him. However, we do see some shortcomings to the Survivor Island approach. First, this exercise classifies as a visually-based projective and therefore, it is a more difficult type of projective than e.g., text-based assignments such as sentence or story completion (Bagnoli, 2009; Kalter, 2016:132-138). As a consequence, Survivor Island will demand a higher amount of creativity on the part of the respondents and the moderators should foresee enough time to conduct the exercise. Second, this type of projective requires substantial preparation in advance i.e., putting together all the materials that are needed for conducting Survivor Island (Kalter, 2016). In the original approach, the list of features to be tested seems to be fixed, while in reality it might be useful to add certain features during the process, or merge multiple features into one new feature. Noteworthy, Kalter emphasizes that one should not feel limited by the specific procedures that he outlines for the Survivor Island approach: "Researchers have the freedom to employ considerable latitude in tweaking the mechanics of these techniques to suit the needs of a particular research study - or to create entirely new ones of their own." (Kalter, 2016: 132). Therefore, we present an alternative and more elaborate approach based on the survivor island technique and we aim to illustrate that our island approach can be used successfully to weigh suggestions and game plans within a big pool of ideas for innovation and sustainable development as well. For example, to evaluate all the initiatives that aim

⁵² Retrieved from [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Survivor_\(U.S._TV_series\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Survivor_(U.S._TV_series)): In the CBS television show *Survivor*, a group of strangers are put on an isolated island. The contestants must provide food, fire, and shelter for themselves. Additionally, they compete in challenges for rewards and immunity from elimination. Each episode, the contestants must vote one of their fellow contestants off the island. The contestants are progressively eliminated from the game until only one remains: "The Sole survivor". This person is usually awarded a cash prize (one million dollars in the American version of the show). The *Survivor* television franchise itself is derived from the *Expedition Robinson* TV series. In February 2018, CBS started to broadcast the 36th season of *Survivor* (CBS Interactive, 2018, retrieved from <https://www.cbs.com/shows/survivor/>).

to contribute to the United Nations' Goals for Sustainable Development⁵³.

3 The Coming of TIA: Some (K)alterations to Steve's Island Approach

The aforementioned procedures can be conducted either as an individual exercise or in a group setting (Kalter, 2016). Notwithstanding, there were some interesting elements in Kalter's description of the guidelines for the individual exercise that especially caught our eye (2016, p. 141):

- The respondents work on their own personal "island". This can be a piece of paper in front of them, or at a station on the whiteboard, while each feature is displayed on separate post-its, all initially contained within the borders of the island;
- Respondents are then asked to rearrange the post-its so that the most desirable features remain and the less desirable ones are "voted off" the island;
- The role of the moderator is identical to the general procedures for *Survivor Island* as described in the previous paragraph.

The characteristics and benefits of Survivor Island as proposed by Kalter (2016), have motivated us to adapt and modify his technique. We have done this with the intent of implementing and using it in two of the Horizon 2020 funded projects that we, imec-SMIT⁵⁴, are currently participating in, the Content Personalisation Network (CPN)⁵⁵ project and HRADIO⁵⁶. In these projects, we used the island approach with the aim of evaluating user requirements and scenarios for the development of inclusive, smart, and innovative media solutions. By doing so, we claim that we have contributed to the validation of Survivor Island as a projective technique useful for qualitative user research and that we were able to broaden its application potential by refining the specific procedures and add some concrete extensions, as we will discuss below. Furthermore, we will demonstrate that we have increased the transferability and versatile use of the "island" approach in a living lab context. We recognize the importance of the island approach for user-driven product and service development (Jespersen, 2008). More specific, we believe this approach is suitable as an evaluation tool to improve the maturity of innovation because it can be used to introduce innovations to target groups and assess their potential on the market (Jespersen, 2008).

⁵³ To explore the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, see: <http://sdg.iisd.org/>

⁵⁴ Have a look at our website: <http://smit.vub.ac.be/>

⁵⁵ CPN project website: <https://www.projectcpn.eu/>

⁵⁶ HRADIO project website: <https://www.hrado.eu/>

As user researchers, we are often confronted with time-related and practical considerations during the data collection phase of a project. In our living lab approach, we strive to involve users early in the process, to ensure a user-centered design approach. However, the first decisions on user scenarios and requirements need to be made early in the project, leaving limited time to organize user involvement. Therefore, we make use of user workshops in which users with different profiles are involved in group discussion and co-creation exercises, with the aim of gathering user scenarios and requirements and/or evaluate these user scenarios and requirements. As these workshops are typically limited to two hours in order not to put too much constraint on the participants, we apply specific techniques to reach the goal of the workshop.

To conform with the time scope and practical concerns, we therefore decided to carry out some changes to the procedures of Survivor Island (Kalter, 2016), to be able to implement it in our user workshops. To start with, we decided not to let participants draw their own island, as is foreseen in the original method, but we developed a more extensive island template (see Fig. 1), that was distributed to the participants during the workshop (A4-size, landscape). In this template, there is still an island as a central feature, but we added some additional dimensions: the sea, the crocodiles, the palm tree on the island and the beach chair. This with the aim of creating a more tangible prioritising exercise.

<h2 style="text-align: center;">The island template</h2>	<p>To support a smooth and efficient performance of the island exercise, we have developed an island template.</p> <p>It is possible to use this template for both the individual and the group island exercise. For conducting the individual exercise, we recommend printing the template on paper (A4-size, landscape orientation). Make sure that you have one printed template per participant. It is not a luxury to foresee some extra prints as well. When performing the group exercise, we advise to print the template in poster size (at least A3-size).</p> <p>On the island template, we have created designated purging zones to guide the participants during the process of voting certain features <i>on</i>, and discarding others <i>off</i>, the island:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crocodiles: In this section (bottom right of the template), the participants place the items which they perceive as not useful or relevant to take with them on the island at all. In other words, the <i>least crucial</i> and <i>weakest</i> features are fed to the crocodiles. • Lifebuoy: This section (upper left corner of the template) does exactly what it promises, it provides a way for participants to “save” certain features. While doing the island exercise, the moderator urges them to keep only the bare essentials in mind. On the lifebuoy, the participants can place the items which they perceive as <i>interesting</i> but <i>not necessary</i> to take with them on the island right now. • Beach chair: The participants are allowed to take only three items with them on the island. Thus, they are encouraged to draw up their top 3 of features. Their number one feature, which they perceive as the strongest and most crucial feature, receives the best spot on the island: in the beach chair at the seaside, on the left of the island. • Palm trees: The item that is assigned second place by the participants, may rest underneath the palm trees. You can find this section on the upper side of the island. • “Exposed” spot, on the bottom of the island: The feature that ranks third, does not receive a fancy seat at the seaside or a place in the shade. This item is placed on the open, “exposed” spot on the bottom of the island. <p>The purging zones do not only guide the participants whilst performing the island exercise, they are also useful for the researcher whilst processing and analysing the data. It is impossible to register everything during the workshop. Audio and video records can help, but the template is an extra way of documenting the data. By looking at the place of features on the island, the researcher is able to identify how they were weighed. Make sure the participants write their names on the template before beginning the exercise!</p>

Figure 1. The Island template

Furthermore, on top of revising the procedures of Survivor Island (Kalter, 2016), we have developed an extension to the exercise. In other words, we have created an island approach add-on and we have named it ‘the luggage tool’. It is an exercise that is to be performed in combination with the island approach. It has proven highly efficient when dealing with a high number of scenarios, features or components that are up for evaluation. Its purpose is to provide a tool for a first elimination round in which the overall number of e.g., scenarios that need to be evaluated, is reduced to a more manageable amount. In this case, a number of scenarios that could be arranged by the participants individually on their own island and afterwards evaluated in-depth during a group discussion. Thus, the luggage tool can be seen as a way of conducting a first scenario selection round, prior to the actual “purging process” during the island exercise. We have provided an example below to illustrate the protocol and utility of the luggage tool as applied in the HRADIO project (see section 3) (Fig. 2).

The luggage tool	
	<p>Imagine the aim of research is to evaluate a large number of user scenarios. Asking participants to evaluate every scenario in a two-hour workshop is too intensive and overwhelming for them. We created an intermediate step to solve this problem, the luggage tool.</p> <p>Protocol: All of the scenarios that are up for evaluation have been assigned a number and hung across the walls of the workshop room. The participants receive a stack of post-its, a pencil, and a luggage template that is printed on a piece of paper. They are instructed to walk around the room and read each scenario attentively. Afterwards, they are asked to select the scenarios that stand out to them the most. To indicate which scenarios they prefer, the participants write down the number of the corresponding scenario on a post-it and stick this on luggage the template.</p> <p>Outcome: One is able to have participants conduct the evaluation exercise, creating their personal “island”, starting from a more manageable number. The advantage of this is, instead of having to process a large number of scenarios, the “purging process” in which the scenarios are weighed mainly focusses on the scenarios that were selected in the participants’ luggage.</p>

Fig. 2: The luggage tool

Additionally, we decided not to use post-it’s to depict the scenarios or features we want to test, but to work with **visualisations** (see Fig. 3 for an example of a scenario visualisation). The motivation not to us

post-its is two-fold. First, most of the time we test scenarios and requirements that need a bit more explanation, so the text would simply not fit onto a post-it.

Second, we prefer to have large depictions of the scenarios or features to be tested on the wall. At the beginning of the island exercise, we instruct participants to walk around and read all scenarios attentively (also see section IV, Fig. 5). They are provided a luggage tool template on which they can write or stick post-its of the numbers corresponding to scenarios that they perceive as interesting to develop in real life. According to us, this contributes to the interactivity of the workshop session because it enhances the motivation and energy level of the participants. E.g., the participants appear more energetic, and engaged in the topic, when they are able to walk around freely and decide for themselves in which order to read and select the scenarios. At the same time, this allows the moderators to walk around and provide additional clarifications where needed, in a more informal way.

S10 STREAMING MEETS BROADCAST

WHAT?

Leon uses his smartphone to chat with friends, to keep up to date with the latest news and to discover new music. He uses streaming apps to personalise his music list but also wants to keep up with the news. With the Hradio app he can make hybrid radio: he can personalise the music he wants to hear, listen to live radio or stream. That way he decides when he wants to hear the news or not. He can simply skip over topics that don't interest him. Additionally, he can assemble a personalised programme for different times of the day so he doesn't have to change his preferences each time. This is convenient as he prefers to just listen to music in the evening, without the news updates. In the morning he likes to be informed about the latest news.

WHY?

👎 Leon sometimes misses the news updates while streaming his own music selection. On other occasions, all he wants to hear is the music, no news.

👍 Leon can create and adapt his own radio experience.

S11 NEW NEWS

WHAT?

Christophe is in the car often. He has just heard the 8 o'clock news. Before, he would have already heard the same news at 7 o'clock, when he just got in the car. But now, Hradio provides Christophe with additional information to the previous news bulletin, such as in-depth journalistic pieces or local football updates.

WHY?

👉 Christophe keeps getting the same general news updates but misses some more in-depth information.

👍 Christophe is informed better and has a deeper understanding of various news topics in addition to keeping track of local news stories as well.

Fig. 3: Examples of scenario visualisations. In this case, scenario 10 'Streaming meets broadcast' and scenario 11 'New news'. Two of the 29 hybrid radio scenarios that were up for evaluation during the user research phase in HRADIO.

9 TIA in practice: the case of HRADIO

In this section of the paper, we present the case of a Horizon 2020 funded research project to explain and illustrate how the island approach translates into practice: HRADIO.

The main focus of HRADIO is sustainable facilitation of new radio services based on multi-level technology convergence, in this case hybrid radio. The goal of the project is to realize attractive new radio services such as the delivery of time- and location independent linear radio seamlessly linked with personalized on-demand content, and this where and whenever the listener demands it (<https://www.hradio.eu/>).

Fig. 4: The HRADIO logo

Within the HRADIO project, we apply a living lab approach, involving all relevant stakeholders from the start of the project. Concretely we are responsible for the work

packages and tasks that focus on user research, piloting, and business development. A first step in the research process was the gathering of different possible user scenarios in dedicated sessions with the project partners and users. These scenarios would serve as the basis for the technical development within the project, so therefore it is crucial that these scenarios are based on actual user needs. Next we organized different user workshops with the aim of evaluating the user scenarios and deriving specific user requirements, as each scenario contained one or more features that had to be evaluated as well. In this section we will first discuss the specific application of TIA in the HRADIO project. Next we will focus on how to process and interpret the outcomes of TIA. By providing specific guidelines and tips, the reader should be able to apply a similar approach in their research projects.

How to apply TIA: the evaluation of user requirements and scenarios in HRADIO

Goal of the workshops

Originally, 47 potential user scenarios were created to define the development of HRADIO applications. These were established to reflect the potential use of hybrid radio in a wide variety of situations (HRADIO, 2017)⁵⁷. HRADIO aims to integrate user feedback in all stages of development. Therefore, we organized workshops with radio listeners to gain insight in their current listening practices, learn more about their preferences, and collect feedback on the defined user scenarios. However, to evaluate 47 scenarios at once, would be a too overwhelming task for the participants. Thus, we decided to perform a clustering of the user scenarios first. This way, the scenarios were not altered significantly but rather consolidated and summarized in a way that is comprehensible for end-users. The 47 original user scenarios were clustered in 10 themes. Similar scenarios in each theme were merged (HRADIO, 2018):

- Timeshifting + cross device listening (S1);
- Timeshifting (S2);
- Timeshifting + personalisation (S3, S4);
- Personalisation (S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S10);
- Personalisation of context (S11, S12, S13, S14, S15, S16);
- Personalisation + interactivity (S17);
- Interactivity (S18, S19, S20, S21);
- Voice control (S22);
- Audio and reception quality (S23, S24);
- Visualisation (S25, S26, S27, S28, S29).

⁵⁷ <https://www.hradio.eu/outcome/>

The clustering exercise led to 29 user scenarios⁵⁸ that were up for evaluation. We set up four evaluation workshops in total, three with end users⁸ and one HRADIO consortium panel workshop. We organized these user evaluation workshops with the objective of gaining insights in the current radio practices of the participants, collecting user feedback on the generated scenarios, and identifying the most desirable scenarios from a user perspective. This enabled us to compare the results of both end-users and the consortium partners. By allowing these 29 scenarios to be evaluated by users, the consortium was able to avoid some of the common pitfalls of technology design e.g., imagining a user that is too flexible or designing a technology for personal use rather than for a general public (Cooper, 2004).

TIA workshop outline, guidelines and tips

In this section, we describe the outline and flow of the island approach workshop. We also provide guidelines and practical tips for conducting a TIA workshop. The procedures that we describe here are appropriate for a workshop with a duration of approximately two hours. We advise that no more than twelve people participate in one island approach workshop, to keep the workshop manageable.

The first part of the workshop is aimed at making the participants feel welcome and get them acquainted with the topic. The moderator briefly explains the goals of the research project, describes the workshop flow, and clarifies what is expected of the participants during the session i.e., they are encouraged to voice anything and everything they are thinking about during the workshop, and it is emphasized that there are no “wrong” answers or opinions. Furthermore, the moderator insists that participants are expected not to interrupt each other while speaking. Then follows a round table discussion which has the goal of encouraging the participants to get acquainted with each other. Depending on the number of participants, this exercise requires 10 to 20 minutes. We advise that the (co-)moderators kick off the round table

⁵⁸ The 29 hybrid radio scenario consisted of: S1 ‘Timeshifting and cross device’, S2 ‘Pause, RWND, FFWD’, S3 ‘Stay informed’, S4 ‘In the Mix’, S5 ‘Music filter’, S6 ‘Local Advertising’, S7 ‘Event Radio’, S8 ‘Radio for kids’, S9 ‘Automatic News-Update’, S10 ‘Streaming meets broadcast’, S11 ‘New News’, S12 ‘News Synopsis’, S13 ‘Automatically Adapted Radio’, S14 ‘Recommended Stations’, S15 ‘No more Traffic Jams!’, S16 ‘Traffic Jammer’, S17 ‘Personalised Interactive Advertising’, S18 ‘New Discoveries’, S19 ‘Push the Button’, S20 ‘Traffic Jam Quiz’, S21 ‘More info’, S22 ‘Voice control’, S23 ‘Guaranteed Signal and Quality’, S24 ‘Radio Butler’, S25 ‘Visual Stories’, S26 ‘Subtitles’, S27 ‘Lyrics’, S28 ‘Logos’, and finally, S29 ‘What is it about?’

⁸ Two end-user workshops were organized in Brussels, Belgium (HRADIO, 2018). The recruitment efforts focused on two participant pools. We invited students to participate in the first workshop. Namely, HRADIO has *“a special interest in youngsters, which represent the segment of the market that more has reduced its radio consumption, but that could also more easily benefit from HRADIO results”* (HRADIO Grant Agreement, part B, p. 31). Nine students participated, 2 men and 7 women, ages 21-24. The second workshop consisted of a heterogeneous group of radio listeners. Six people participated, 1 man and 5 women, ages 20-42. Both of these workshops were conducted in Dutch. The third end-user workshop took place in Potsdam, Germany. This workshop was conducted in German. Five film students and two researchers participated, 4 men and 3 women, ages 26-39.

discussion, by starting with the following set-up to introduce themselves, so that participants will follow the same structure:

- Name;
- Occupation / field of study;
- Something related to the research topic, in HRADIO we used a short description of 'how I listen to radio'.

The participants are asked to introduce themselves and describe their own radio listening habits to the group. If possible, the moderator should ask follow-up questions e.g.: 'What do you like and dislike about radio? How can radio be improved? Which radio assets or features are currently missing according to you?' The co-moderator takes notes of this part of the session e.g., (s)he creates a visualisation on a flipchart of the participants' answers in a positives and negatives overview.

After the introduction part of the workshop, it is time for scenario evaluation. This happens in two consecutive stages: first, a selection of appealing scenarios. Different concept-clusters are displayed throughout the room on big post-its. As also described in the previous section of this paper (see above), for HRADIO there are ten concept-clusters in total. Each concept-cluster is a collection of related scenarios that were generated earlier in the user research phase of the project. Every scenario has its' own number. Participants are asked to go through the scenarios individually, they can walk from poster to poster (Fig. 5). Each participant is provided a luggage template. We advise to urge that participants write their names on the template so the template can be linked to the respondents in the analysis phase. From the total of 29 scenarios we ask them to select a maximum of 10 scenarios that they would prefer to see realized. For each preferred scenario, they write the number on a post-it note and stick it on their personal "radio-suitcase". To conclude the scenario-selection stage, a group discussion follows in which the participants explain one by one why they chose certain scenarios over others. The reasons for similarities and differences between choices are discussed e.g., 'Did other participants pick the same scenarios? Why or why not?' If you are dealing with a large number of scenarios, like the evaluation of 29 hybrid radio scenarios in the HRADIO project, it is advised to foresee about 30 minutes for the luggage exercise and 15-20 minutes to discuss the selected scenarios.

Figure 5. Pictures taken at a HRADIO workshop whilst participants are performing the luggage exercise. They select the scenarios that stand out to them most by sticking the corresponding scenario numbers onto their luggage template.

As a second step in the scenario evaluation, we introduce the projective “island” exercise. After the discussion on the choices of scenarios, each participant is asked to take its suitcase to his/her personal “island”. An island template is provided for each participant. The moderators should foresee 15 to 30 minutes to conduct this assignment. The participants are asked to rank their personal selection of scenarios according to how ‘interesting’, ‘relevant’ or ‘necessary’ they perceive the scenarios when these would be developed as a feature or service for hybrid radio in real-life. They are instructed to assign the post-its in their “radio-suitcase” a place on the “island”. Each place on the island has a different meaning in terms of priority. We provide an example of the island template and an in-depth description of its procedures in section III (see Fig. 1).

To finish the workshop, each participant presents its island to the group. Afterwards, a group discussion is held about the results of the island-exercise. The closing discussion should take about 15 to 20 minutes. Interesting questions here would be:

- ‘Which scenarios are most placed in the beach chair and why?’
- Which scenarios would the participants love to see realized? Why?’
- Which scenarios were thrown to the crocodiles and why?’
- Which scenarios would be least interesting in real life? Why?’

The motivations for keeping or eliminating certain scenarios were recorded on audio and integrated in the qualitative analysis process afterwards. This way we also captured the evaluation of each scenario and why it should or shouldn’t be included. During the last five minutes of the workshop, we ask each participant individually whether they have any final thoughts to add to the discussion e.g., to the set-up and exercises used in the workshop.

How to process and interpret the outcomes of TIA: the example of scores and rankings

Now, imagine that we conducted both the luggage and island exercise today. How can we process and analyze this data? How can we interpret the outcomes? In other words, how can we make sense of the evaluation exercises that were performed? In the case of HRADIO, we chose to deal with this by assigning scores and drawing up rankings. This means that all 29 scenarios that were up for evaluation received a score.

We adhered to the following conditions:

- If a scenario was not selected into the participants' luggage then it receives 0 points;
- If a scenario was selected in the participants' luggage, but it was not assigned in the top three items that are on the island, then the scenario is awarded 1 point;
- The scenario that placed third, allocated on the "exposed" spot on the bottom of the island, receives 3 points;
- The second-best scenario, which is placed near the palm trees on the upper side of the island, is granted 4 points;
- Finally, 5 points are awarded to the scenario that placed first: the one sitting in the beach chair at the seaside on the left of the island.

After we assigned a score to each scenario, we were able to draw up rankings of the scenarios that were evaluated during the workshop. The benefit of this is, we could then compare rankings against each other. For example, in the HRADIO project we compared the top ten ranking of scenarios by end users against the consortium ranking (Fig. 6). This allowed us to look for similarities and discrepancies between the evaluation of HRADIO scenarios by end users and consortium members. E.g., determine the shared top ten scenarios by the end users and the consortium (also see Fig. 6, indicated in bold). By applying a mixed methods approach (Creswell, 2003) in our analysis by integrating a more quantitative approach as a supportive technique to the analysis of our qualitative data (i.e. motivations and appraisal of each scenario), we believe that we are able to provide a detailed and motivated selection of scenarios.

End user ranking		Consortium ranking	
Nr.	Name	Nr.	Name
1	Time-shifting and cross-device listening	1	Time-shifting and cross-device listening
4	In the mix	18	New discoveries
5	Music filter	12	News synopsis
18	New discoveries	4	In the mix
3	Stay informed	27	Lyrics
23	Guaranteed signal quality	5	Music filter
27	Lyrics	25	Visual stories
14	Recommended stations	19	Push the button
10	Streaming meets broadcast	10	Streaming meets broadcast
16	Traffic jammer	21	More info

Table 5: Overview of end user ranking versus overview of consortium ranking

Fig. 6: Overview of the end-user ranking versus overview of the HRADIO consortium ranking.

This section of the paper comes to an end, by considering how one can interpret the outcomes of the island exercise. As also illustrated by the example of HRADIO in the paragraph above, the results allow the researcher to determine for e.g., overlap in the selection and evaluation of certain scenarios by two

different parties. In addition, it is possible to look for discrepancies as well. For example, which scenarios are selected by one group but not by another, and why? It is important however, to emphasize that the rankings that result from the island approach are not grounded in quantitative research. They do not hold ‘numerical’ value. They are used to provide qualitative interpretations of e.g., how end users perceive and appraise individual scenarios for hybrid radio, or how they weigh certain scenarios against each other. Furthermore, as the research sample is not representative, the outcomes of the island exercise cannot be generalised.

This does not mean that the outcomes of the island exercise are not relevant in an iterative, co-creation development process. For example, if we had approached the HRADIO scenario evaluation solely in a quantitative way, this would have resulted in purely numerical rankings. If we now presume that in such a case, we also had a representative research sample, yes, then maybe we would have been able to determine with certitude which scenarios ranked higher or lower than others. This however, would still not be enough to attest for the reasons why the scenarios were evaluated that way. This unequivocally confirms that a qualitative research approach was needed to answer these questions. What is more, the advantage of putting such a lens on our research topic was that items that received a ‘negative’ evaluation, often

resulting in a 'low' overall ranking, did not necessarily lead to excluding these scenarios from the next steps in the project. In other words, the qualitative user evaluation did not bias taking these scenarios into consideration for further revision, with the purpose of adding them to the pilot selection. We exemplify this in the figure below (Fig. 7). The figure is based on the recommendations that we made after having completed the evaluation of scenarios for hybrid radio, concerning the next steps in the HRADIO project in general and how to proceed for the pilots in particular (HRADIO, 2018).

The case of HRADIO: recommendations for further development of the scenarios into pilots after the completion of the evaluation phase	
What do the rankings mean?	The rankings show that these cases tap into real needs or desires of users. They express beliefs and attitudes of the user concerning which service would or would not be sufficiently interesting.
How to interpret the outcomes of this evaluation exercise?	By approaching the evaluation workshops in a qualitative way, we were able to inquire why the scenarios, and certain user requirements in particular, were considered interesting. Our research approach provided insight into the affordances, advantages and disadvantages for users associated with each scenario. In the end, there appeared to be a strong overlap for 6 scenarios in the top ten ranking of the end users and the HRADIO consortium. The resemblance between the two overall rankings served as an indication of which scenarios were considered most relevant to take into the next phases of the user research and pilot activities of the HRADIO project.
What is inferred by a 'negative' evaluation e.g., what does a low-ranking scenario imply?	The ranking of scenarios was not the only determinant on which we based ourselves for taking certain scenarios into consideration to develop as pilots or services. For example, the workshop approach allowed the participants to voice their rationale for voting certain items on and off the "island". Because of this, we discovered that certain scenarios are not perceived as interesting to develop as a pilot or service as such. This does not mean that they are not interesting or relevant at all. Therefore, these scenarios were not yet excluded from the HRADIO project. In the future, they could be integrated as features in other scenarios. For example, the evaluation of voice control and visual story scenarios. These appeared to have no clear benefit for participants in the end user workshops. For the case of voice control, this was linked to negative past experiences. When concerning visual stories, this was due to a lack of experience of the user. They simply could not imagine a concrete setting in which radio visualisations would be an asset. Nevertheless, the negative evaluation by the end user did not necessarily result in eliminating the relevance of integrating voice control or visual story features in HRADIO completely. Both the end users and the consortium members indicated that they perceive voice control and visual stories as interesting features for HRADIO. Maybe not right now, but definitely when the technology is more mature and thus, more accessible to use. Hence, this once more proves the richness and diversity of data that is generated through conducting co-creation workshops.
What are the next steps to validate the outcomes of this exercise?	We organised workshops and asked end users to evaluate 29 hybrid radio scenarios. We also organized a similar workshop with the members of the HRADIO consortium. The qualitative evaluation exercise resulted into two overall scenario rankings, one by the end users and one by the consortium. This allowed us to look for overlap and discrepancies. It also supported us when creating a short list of scenarios, a comparison between the top ten rankings of scenarios by the end users and the consortium. This short list was then revised from a technical perspective. The analysis revealed that certain scenarios potentially overlap in terms of technical requirements. E.g., according to the technical partners in the HRADIO consortium, the development of a 'music filter' is not that different from creating a component to 'filter out irrelevant traffic information'. Correspondingly, we recommended to perform a clustering of the 29 scenarios from a technical perspective, before revisiting the qualitative evaluation by users for the HRADIO pilots. The next steps in validating the outcomes of the user scenario evaluation are therefore, a technical clustering of the scenarios, rewriting scenarios as features, and to define pilots based on the previous steps and on the insights of the user evaluation.

Figure 7. Recommendations for further development of the scenarios into pilots after the completion of the evaluation phase (HRADIO, 2018, pp. 59- 60)

10 Evaluation and discussion of TIA

In these final passages, we recapitulate and reflect on how we revised the procedures of the island approach. We reminisce on our experiences while applying this projective technique and discuss its strengths and weaknesses. We demonstrate the transferability of the island exercise by exhibiting its suitability for purposes other than evaluating. The paper comes to an end by illustrating the versatile use of the approach through emphasizing how TIA could contribute in realizing the United Nations' Goals for Sustainable Development (SDG Knowledge Hub, 2018).

To summarize, we predominantly tweaked the procedures that were originally proposed by Steve Kalter (2016) for the individual Survivor Island exercise. We were particularly inspired by the ability of Survivor Island for having participants work on their own "island". The benefit of asking respondents to work independently on a projective exercise before a group discussion is that any bias from other participants' influencing responses is mitigated (Kalter, 2016:132). Furthermore, we perceived Kalter's projective technique as well-suited because the Survivor Island exercise allows participants to "project" themselves into a situation that is otherwise rather abstract to imagine for them. For example, to evaluate requirements for technologies that are still in development and are therefore, not yet available to the general public. Therefore, the approach perfectly fits the needs of a research project such as HRADIO. Thus, we used this inspiration to transform the individual island exercise into an approach that fitted the methodological needs of the user research phase in HRADIO. We then combined our adapted island approach with the role of the moderator as explained by Kalter (2016) in the general procedures for Survivor Island. That is to say, we completely agree with him that (co-)moderators are needed to support the "purging process", and to encourage participants to voice their rationale for either keeping on or casting off certain scenarios.

Our motivations for developing TIA were mainly 'practice'-oriented (Mårtensson et al, 2016). We adopted a grounded, abductive and inductive research approach throughout the development and revision of TIA, and when conducting TIA in practice (Bryman, 2016; Mårtensson et al, 2016). In other words, 'knowledge' was produced in the 'context of application', also referred to as 'knowing in action' or 'situated learning' (Mårtensson et al, 2016:594).

The Island Approach	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Fun, easy-going exercise that contributes to a dynamic workshop experience. The interactive aspect of the approach energizes participants and improves their engagement in the discussion topic. The island assignment can be conducted individually or as group exercise.</p> <p>Very useful projective technique for evaluating a large number of possibilities and ideas. When the number of items that have to be evaluated is rather extensive, it is nevertheless recommended to create visualisations. These visuals, be it textual or graphic, will help the participants to envision scenarios that are up for evaluation.</p>	<p>This projective requires substantial preparation in advance e.g., organising the workshops and preparation of materials. Furthermore, conducting an island approach workshop demands a high level of facilitation, at least one moderator and a facilitator should be present.</p> <p>Because this a visually-based projective, it demands a higher level of creativity on the part of the respondents. Providing visualisations and descriptions of the items that need to be evaluated can certainly provide solace to some extent. We decided to create textual visualisations but we have noticed that i.e., having to read 29 scenario-texts, is sometimes still too exhausting for participants. We suggest two potential solutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One could bundle scenario-texts into a 'booklet' and provide this and the island template to the participants. You ask them to prepare the exercise as 'homework' prior to the workshops. The outcomes of these individual assignments could then function as starting point for a group discussion during the workshop itself. • Second, instead of using purely textual visualisations, one could create a more graphic solution i.e., visual stories or cartoons, or provide a combination of both.
<p>This qualitative evaluation tool allows researchers to gain insight in the motivations and reasons of participants for selecting certain scenarios, and for eliminating others. By conducting the island approach, you do not only learn <i>which</i> scenarios were evaluated in a 'positive' or 'negative' manner, you also find out <i>why</i>. In addition, the outcomes of the island exercise allow for a diverse range of ways to <i>visualise</i> the results. One could opt for scores and rankings but there exist other options as well. For example, the outcome of the individual island exercises could be visualised in a group island, a "<i>meta-island</i>", representing all individual preferences.</p>	<p>No ready-to-go results, the outcomes of this technique demand quite some processing. For example, creating an overview of the collected data demands a considerable amount of time and effort. Moreover, you need to find an appropriate way to make sense of the data. In the case of HRADIO, scores and rankings proved most useful to reach our research goals. However, these rankings held no real 'numeric' value. The outcomes of the workshops could not be generalized. This was due to our choice for a qualitative evaluation approach and because we did not focus on a representative sample. If the aim of research is to create a quantitative examination of the extent in which scenarios are evaluated in a positive or negative manner, we deem TIA suitable as well but we advise to revise its procedures through a quantitative lens.</p>
<p>Researchers are permitted to tweak the procedures and mechanics of this projective technique to suit the needs of a particular research study (Kalter, 2016).</p>	<p>Kalter does not provide examples or real-life applications when describing the procedures for <i>Survivor Island</i> (2016). We too are currently not in the knowledge of cases in which the island approach was applied by other researchers. We hope to provide a first validation and revision of the island approach through this paper. However, we also recommend further validation of the approach before it can be labelled as a fully-developed 'method' for evaluating e.g., 'the maturity of innovation' cf. Jespersen (2008).</p>

Fig. 8: The strengths and weaknesses of The Island Approach

Strengths and weaknesses

To support our evaluation of TIA, we organized an internal workshop with our peer living lab researchers at imec-smit, Vrije Universiteit Brussel in which we demonstrated and discussed the exercise. The outcome was a set of strengths and weaknesses of the island approach, as summarized in Fig. 8.

The strengths the island approach respond to e.g., design-thinking experts asking for alternative, 'creative' approaches that keep research participants engaged and focus on the needs and experiences of humans as the primary motivating factor to evaluate innovation actions (Dam & Siang, 2018). TIA helps to create "a new space that encourages everyone, not just academics, to come together to create a new platform for the 21st century: a new place, a new way of thinking, a new way of doing." (Ito, 2017). This adds to the suitability of TIA as a tool for co-creation, namely, conducting the island exercise creates "dynamic spaces, both physically and metaphorically, where people are able to embrace change, explore the unknown, experiment with radically new ways of thinking, and work together collaboratively." (Dam & Siang, 2018). Hence, TIA answers to the need for methods and tools that enhance collaboration and encourage shared vision between stakeholders at an early stage in the research or development process (Laing & Todd, 2015).

TIA being a creative, visual method makes it suitable to overcome the limitations of talk-based approaches such as interviews and focus groups (Buckingham, 2009; Bryman, 2016). It provides an alternative to the hegemony of 'word-and-number based academy' (Prosser & Loxley, 2008). The technique gives participants 'something to look at', something to 'create', and helps to 'bridge the gap' and build connections between the researcher and the researched (Gauntlett & Holzwarth, 2006; Laing & Todd, 2015; Prosser & Loxley, 2008). The exercise enables the subjects of research to express their views more instantly and directly, and with less interference from the researcher, which is more empowering for research participants and avoids treating individuals as mere 'audiences' of products (Buckingham, 2009; Gauntlett & Holzwarth, 2006; Prosser & Loxley, 2008). It allows participants to work at their own pace to shape the research 'agenda' and decide what is 'important' (Laing & Todd, 2015).

There exist other, more 'traditional' approaches as well that make use of visual and spatial arrangement to elicit immediacy, enhance the possibility for iterative research design, and to reduce "singular truths" (Laing & Todd, 2015:23). For example, concept-mapping tools such as the Ishikawa or fishbone diagram, timeline-mediated interviewing, and diamond rankings (Laing & Todd, 2015). However, when compared

to TIA, these types of exercises are more abstract to understanding and developing

ideas (Laing & Todd, 2015).

The weaknesses of TIA emphasize that visual 'creative' approaches, in themselves, are not any more empowering than other methods nor do they in themselves provide greater opportunities for 'participation' (Buckingham, 2009). In addition, these approaches require a greater amount of 'reflexivity' on the side of research participants and require focus on the formative role and responsibilities of the researcher (Buckingham, 2009). What is more, similar to Buckingham (2009), we too experienced that data from a 'creative' research approach such as the island exercise cannot be taken at face value; there is currently still a lack of methods that "deal specifically with the visual dimensions of such material, rather than falling back on participants verbal account" (p. 648). While various methods have been tried and tested, no 'one-size-fits-all' approach has yet been found (Buckingham, 2009), "at present the most common mixed method designs are used to span the quantitative and qualitative divide and there are insufficient models or exemplars of the contributive role visual methods could play." (Prosser & Loxley, 2008:36-37).

Nevertheless, we conclude that when TIA is used in combination with other methods e.g., during a co-creation workshop, the visual and creative character of the island exercise results in a more 'engaging' and 'enjoyable' experience for the research participants (Buckingham, 2009; Gauntlett & Holzwarth, 2006). Because TIA requires a greater amount of creativity and reflexivity, the outcome of the exercise is to the result of 'thoughtful reflection' (Gauntlett & Holzwarth, 2006). Furthermore, TIA encourages 'collaborative production' and 'participatory research' (Buckingham, 2009). Therefore, the island exercise is particularly appropriate for media and social research because in these fields "the method should follow the object" (Buckingham, 2009:634). TIA is not solely a visual means of recording data, but a medium through which new knowledge and critiques may be created (Pink, 2006).

Transferability: the suitability of TIA for purposes other than evaluating

With this paper, we have illustrated that the island approach is appropriate when the aim of research is to evaluate a large number of user requirements and scenarios. Therefore, we appeal to adopt TIA in your methodological toolbox for evaluation of the 'learning curve' and 'maturity of innovations' (Jespersen, 2008). What is more, we presume that the island approach is useful for the 'generation of ideas' as well. Provided that some revisions to its procedures are necessary when the aim of research is 'idea generation', TIA could be applied during the 'exploration' and 'ideation' phase in research projects

to have different stakeholders brainstorm in an efficient way to conceptualize a

product or service (Jespersen, 2008).

For example, in the case of HRADIO the research had already resulted in 29 hybrid radio scenarios that needed to be evaluated by end users before we were able to continue with the next stages in the project i.e., to decide which of the scenarios we are going to pilot. Imagine however, that we were still at the beginning of the research project and that our aim was to generate ideas and scenarios for hybrid radio. The island approach would also be suitable for this. One could start a TIA workshop by providing a luggage template to the participants and ask them to think about interesting ideas and features for hybrid radio, write these down on post-its, and stick these on their luggage. It would then be interesting to develop a new, intermediate 'elimination round' e.g., an 'airport and customs tool'. You tell the participants that when they arrive at the airport, the customs officer notices that they have "packed" too much in their suitcase. The participants are only allowed to take the 'bare essentials' with them on the plane and therefore, they must eliminate at least 3 items from their suitcase. We advise the moderator to inquiry why participants want to keep or remove certain items from their luggage. You continue the workshop by conducting the island exercise. The focus lies on weighing the ideas in the participants' suitcases by allocating them a place on the island, the procedures for the island exercise remain similar to what we have described in section IV.

Versatility: how TIA could contribute to the United Nations' Goals for Sustainable Development

To conclude, we have delved and immersed ourselves into the island approach. We have experienced its flexibility and versatility in use and we will surely apply it again in the future. The island approach does exactly what one expects of an effective projective technique: it helps participants to "project" and engage themselves in a situation that would otherwise be rather difficult to imagine. E.g., it supports them in envisioning and evaluating technological innovations that are not yet available on the market or to the general public. TIA is especially suitable as a tool for co-creation considering it is indeed a fun and easy-going exercise that is accessible for stakeholders of many different sorts. We noticed that the island approach can bring about the potential in people of thinking about problem solutions from their own perspective, but it also encourages them to "think outside the box" and to look upon issues from other perspectives⁵⁹.

⁵⁹ **Anecdote:** When we conducted the island approach in co-creation workshops with end-users and consortium partners of the HRADIO project, the projective technique had a remarkable effect. It did not only elicit reactions from the users and the consortium partners on how they weighed scenarios from their own perspective, meaning as either an end-user or a consortium partner, the exercise also provoked them to voice what the other party would - or "should" - think. Thus, the island approach has contributed in encouraging both parties to take the perspective of other stakeholders into account. Therefore, the island approach truly embodies

TIA is significantly fit for a living lab approach because the flexibility of its procedures allow researchers to conduct the island exercise in both the exploration and evaluation phase of a project. We believe that people who want to design, develop and evaluate solutions that meet the United Nations' Goals for Sustainable Development could definitely benefit from this. The island approach could for example, be applied to generate ideas and evaluate initiatives that contribute to one of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG Knowledge Hub, 2018) or one of the overarching sustainable development tracks⁶⁰. To be more practical, one could conduct the island exercise e.g., to research how actors of the quadruple helix perceive and assess initiatives that aim to enhance 'quality education'. TIA could function as a qualitative evaluation tool that not only provides insight in which ideas and solutions are perceived as 'relevant' or 'appealing' to develop in real life, but also elicits the reasons why certain initiatives might be more or less 'interesting' than others to pursue. As a consequence, TIA allows researchers and designers to gain insights into how likely users are to adopt or reject certain elements or dimensions of innovations at a very early stage in the design process.

an exercise that is to be performed e.g., when wanting to avoid the mistake of designing a technology for personal use rather than for the general public (Cooper, 2004).

⁶⁰ The European Network of Living Labs has grouped the United Nations' 17 different themes for Global Sustainable Development in 5 tracks which represent the focus of its Living Lab community: Track 1 'Good health and well-being' (SD goals 1,2,3,6), Track 2 'Quality Education' (SD goals 4,5,8,10), Track 3 'Affordable & clean energy' (SD goals 7, 12, 14), Track 4 'Industry, innovation & infrastructure' (SD goals 9, 16, 17), and Track 5 'Sustainable cities & communities' (SD goals 11, 13, 15) (see <https://openlivinglabdays.com/>).

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